

POTENTIALITY OF CAPPARIS DECIDUA (FORSK) EDGEW AGAINST E. COLI AND STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS

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ABSTRACT:

Majority of population from rural areas, tribal and the poor people in urban areas rely mainly on traditional medicines to meet their primary and daily health care needs. The present investigation deals that antibacterial activity of *Capparis decidua* (Forsk) Edgew. The ethanolic extract of *Capparis decidua* subjected to antibiotic activity by using two test organism that is *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. And the results revealed that the *Capparis decidua* have the prominent antibiotic activity against both test organism that is *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Keywords-Antibacterial activity, *Capparis decidua* (Forsk) Edgew, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

INTRODUCTION: -

Human beings are depended on nature for their simple requirements as being the sources for medicines, shelters, food stuffs, fragrances, clothing, flavors, fertilizers and means of transportation throughout the ages. For the large proportions of world's population medicinal plants continue to show a dominant role in the healthcare system and this is mainly true in developing countries, where herbal medicine has continuous history of long use. The development and recognition of medicinal and financial aids of these plants are on rise in both industrialized and developing nations [1].

The genus *Capparis* comprises 250 species including shrubs, trees and woody climbers. *Capparis decidua* (Forsk.) Edgew commonly known as karel, karer, karil, karu etc, is a densely branching shrub or small tree of the Thar Desert [2]. It is also found in the subtropical and tropical zones and other arid regions in southern Asia with a mass of slender, 4-5 m high, or occasionally a small tree with many green vinelike apparently leafless branches, hanging in bundles. The bark turns into whitish-grey colour with age, but most of the branches and twigs are a glossy dark green in colour. Small, light brown spines occur in pairs on the twigs at each node. Leaves are very minute

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(2 mm long), with a very short life span on young shoots, so that the plant looks leafless most of the time. The new flush of leaves appears in November January. Flowers are pink in colour, red-veined, in small groups along the leafless shoots, in the axils of the spines. Red conspicuous flowers appear in March to April and August-September and ripe by May and October.

Material and Method

Collection of plant materials:

The *Capparis decidua* (Forsk) Edgew collected from Ahmednagar district. With the help of referring Flora Of Ahmednagar.

Preparation of extracts:

Plant material washed thoroughly and chopped into small pieces by using mortar and pestle. It is shade dried and grinded into powdered form. Extract was prepared by using ethanol with the help of Soxhlet Apparatus.

Isolation of pathogens:

Two test pathogens *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* used in this study.

Loopful of suspension streaked on ATCC. 8739 and ATCC-6538 on two slants of preincubated Nutrient agar. The slants were incubate at 30-35°C for 24 hours in an incubator After incubation the growth of organism pick up from incubated slant and inoculated in 3 ml of saline solution and vortex to prepare the uniform suspension. Adjusted the O.D. of culture to approx. 60-70 % OD at 530 nm using sterile saline and calorimeter. After adjusting O.D. the test organism stored in refrigeration at 2-80C

Plate Preparation for analysis:

From the prepared suspension 2 ml of culture suspension of *S.auers*, *E.coli* is inoculate separately in 200 ml of sterile molten and cooled medium at 40°C - 45°C 15-20 ml of Sterilized agar medium (Antibiotic Assay Medium No. 19.) is poured into a sterile Petri plate with the help of sterile measuring cylinder give a depth of 3 to 4 mm. Allowed to cool at room temperature by placing the dishes or plates on a level surface. Plates were kept into refrigerator for 15 to 20 minute for hardening. Ensure that the layers of medium are uniform in thickness. 4-5 agar cups on each plate was prepared using 6 mm SS borer. Plates were labeled for sample, standard and negative control samples and analysis details.

Analysis: The volume of solution added to each cylinder or cavity must be uniform and sufficient almost to fill the holes when these are used. 100 µl 1mg/ml Solution A is added to agar cup and labeled as STD.

Add 100 µl 1mg/ml = Solution B to agar cup labeled for each compound ID labeled on plate. Add 100 µl DMSO to agar cup labeled as N (Negative). Leave the dishes or plates standing for 15-20 min. at 2-8°C or as appropriate, as a period of pre- incubation diffusion to minimize the effects of variation in time between the applications of the different solutions. Incubate them for about 24-48 hours at the temperature 30-35°C for bacteria and 20-25°C for yeast and mould. After completion of incubation the diameters or areas of the circular inhibition zones accurately measured and results were

Result: Plate showing Antibacterial activity of *Capparis decidua* (Forsk) Edgew on *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Observation Table:

CONCLUSION: -

Sr.No	Sample	Concentration	Zone of Inhibition (mm)	
			<i>S.aureus</i>	<i>E.coli</i>
1.	Control		-	-
2.	<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forsk) Edgew.	100 µl	20	10
		200µl	23	15
3	Standard Streptomycin	1 mg/ml	25	30

The antibacterial evaluation of *Capparis decidua* (Forsk) Edgew against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli* revealed a clear concentration-dependent activity. At 100 µl, the sample showed a moderate inhibitory effect with zones of 20 mm and 10 mm, respectively. Increasing the

concentration to 200 µl enhanced the activity, producing inhibition zones of 23 mm against *S. aureus* and 15 mm against *E. coli*.

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